

Participation of the 是shì Element in the Copula Function

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Abstract. *In this article, comments on the formation of the element 是shì as a conjunction in the Chinese language are presented. Examples of its being a means of connecting horses and cattle are given with theoretical knowledge.*

Key words: *subject, participle, copula, false-copula, logical accent, verb-conjunction.*

A separate clause is a special type of conjunction. A compound sentence is a complex sentence in which a simple sentence is used as a subject and a subordinate clause.¹

Patten points out that in certain languages, clause clauses belong to a special category of clauses because they are relative clauses containing a general restrictive but non-referential set of definite noun phrases made or made. can be. In other words, sentences with separated clauses appear as part of compound sentences, in which the possibility of interpretation of the noun compound used after the conjunction is limited, as a separate explanation for this compound, the second part of the compound sentence is a relative clause. is presented in the form In addition, a shortened compound can represent not only things, but also actions and signs, so the corresponding units attached to the clause after the conjunction can move between the clauses.²

In dictionaries, as well as in linguistic literature, the general definition of the word "conjunction" is as follows:

The term conjunction is defined as "a word that connects a possessor and a participle"..

In our opinion, the above-mentioned features of the Chinese separated clause clause device belong to the category of annotated clauses, because the application expressed by the possessive noun phrase is without a limited application following the conjunction indicated by the clause. including structure. From the point of view of information content, the conjunction construction in Chinese can also take the place of a logical emphasis. A post-conjunctive unit is a clause in which the speaker or hearer receives a logical emphasis that confirms the presupposed idea. For example, 他是昨天去上海的 [tā shì zuótiān qù shànghǎi de] – *He went to Shanghai yesterday* in the example of counterpoint zuótiān “yesterday” relative tense and presupposition in the context *He went to Shanghai at a certain time*. Likewise, 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – In the case of this prepared place being a house, the counterpoint is represented by the element following the conjunction 是shì, e.g. zàijiā “at home”. If他是去上海的 [tā shì qù shànghǎi de] – When the verb comes directly after the conjunction

¹ Randolph Quirk, Sidney Greenbaum, Geoffrey Leech and Jan Svartvik. *A Comprehensive Grammar of English Language*. – London and New York: Longman. 1985. – 1779 p.; Stephen Levinson. *Pragmatics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983. – P. 301-314.

² Amanda Patten. *Cleft Sentences, construction grammar and grammaticalization*. – Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh, 2010. – P. 45-50.

in a connected sentence, as in the example of *He went to Shanghai*, the focus of the contrast is *qù* “to go” depending on the context. can be the complement of or the verb *qù Shànghǎi* “to go to Shanghai”. According to some scholars, for example, Teng, Zhu, Huang, the conjunction is not repeated in Chinese, on the contrary, 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – the example of *This prepared place was a house* expresses equality, and therefore has and the part can change its position. According to them, 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – *This prepared place was a house* and 在家做的是这个 [zàijiā zuò de shì zhège] – *The examples prepared at home* have the same equivalent meaning and are pseudo-gardens. are lame sentences

Repetition in this place is accepted by the above scientists as a criterion for distinguishing a false connection from the main connection. However, the theoretical validity of using linguistic repetition to describe the linguistic aspects of analysis and synthesis is problematic because it may place unrealistic constraints on linguistic descriptions..

In our opinion, connected and pseudo-connected sentences are not equal, they do not repeat each other. 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – *This prepared place was home* example is a pseudo-conjunction in Modern Chinese 在家做的是这个 [zàijiā zuò de shì zhège] – differs from *This prepared at home* , because they have different forms and mean different things

这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – The sentence in the example of *This prepared place was a house* is not a false conjunction, but the conjunction itself, it contains a special meaning and emphasizes the contrast represents 他是昨天去上海的 [tā shì zuótiān qù shànghǎi de] – *He went to Shanghai yesterday* and 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de]– *This prepared place was a house* is also an example of conjunction construction, but they differ in the optionality of the semantic relation 的 *de* nominalizer. 他是昨天去上海的 [tā shì zuótiān qù shànghǎi de] – In the example, *He went to Shanghai yesterday*, the owner of the sentence “她tā” expresses meaning together with the hidden owner of the nominalizer, and the nominalizer *dede* at the end of the sentence is optional. On the contrary, 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – *This prepared place was a house* in the structure, the possessor of the sentence comes together with the hidden possessive 这个zhège, and the nominalizer *dede* is obligatory. Therefore, within the construct, the schema link construct will have two sub-schemas; bundle-holder 他是昨天去上海的 [tā shì zuótiān qù shànghǎi de] – *He went to Shanghai yesterday* and bundle-filler 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de]– *This prepared place was home*. Conjunction includes possessive relation and nominalizer *dede* optionality. The conjunction-complement includes the possessive-complement relationship, that is, the verb in the nominalization cannot be intransitive.

Huang notes that conjunctions do not have the same meaning as simple conjunctions, noting that “They cannot express equality or conjunction, nor existence like simple conjunctions”. Therefore, he emphasizes that the conjunction 是shì in connected sentences cannot be considered as a linking verb. It proves that syntactically, the conjunction shìshì has the adverbial status. According to Huang, the following examples are connected sentences with *dede* preposition omitted: 小李是昨天打了小王 [Xiǎo lǐ shì zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] – *Xiaoli hit Xiaowang yesterday; Xiaoli hit Xiaowang yesterday.* 是小李昨天打了小王 [shì xiǎo lǐ zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] – *It was Xiaoli who hit Xiaowang yesterday.*

Thus, Huang argues that the conjunction 是shì in connected clauses “has the status of negation and modals.”³

³ O’sha asar.

Therefore, Huang believes that there is a fixed base-changing relationship between the emphasis and the assumption gap. However, he noted that the situation with the Chinese link is completely different. In modern Chinese, “a conjunction is distinguished from a non-conjunction only by the presence or absence of the emphatic *shìshì*. There is no open change of accent.” The clear form of the above examples without conjunction is: 小李昨天打了小王 [Xiǎo lǐ zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] - Yesterday Xiaoli hit Xiaowang.

According to Huang, the simplest way to form conjunctions in Chinese is to place the conjunction *shìshì* directly in front of an emphatic constituent. For example, 小李是昨天打了小王 [Xiǎo lǐ shì zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] – Xiaoli hit Xiaowang yesterday; 小李昨天是打了小王 [Xiǎo lǐ zuótiān shì dǎle xiǎo wáng] – Xiaoli beat Xiaowang yesterday; 是 小李昨天打了小王 [shì xiǎo lǐ zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] – Like *It was Xiaoli who hit Xiaowang yesterday*. Connected sentences in Chinese “unlike other languages, do not involve either a structural connection or a base-variable relationship between stress and predicate.”⁴ He points out that 这个是在家做的 [zhège shì zàijiā zuò de] – *This prepared place was a house*, as in the sentence, as a linking verb of 是 *shì*, is a simple conjunction 是 *shì* or pseudo- garden Considering 是 *shì* is both semantically and syntactically unreasonable. Semantically 小李是昨天打了小王 [Xiǎo lǐ shì zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] – *Xiaoli hit Xiaowang yesterday*; 小李昨天是打了小王 [Xiǎo lǐ zuótiān shì dǎle xiǎo wáng] – *Xiaoli beat Xiaowang yesterday*; Linked clauses such as 是 小李昨天打了小王 [shì xiǎo lǐ zuótiān dǎle xiǎo wáng] - *It was Xiaoli who hit Xiaowang yesterday* - do not express unity of equality, definiteness, connection or conjunction. Syntactically, one of the important restrictions on conjunction formation is that no pre-verb phrase can act as a conjunction. Therefore, 小李昨天打了是 小王 [Xiǎo lǐ zuótiān dǎle shì xiǎo wáng] – *It was Xiaoli who hit Xiaowang yesterday* is not grammatically correct.

If the conjunction 是 *shì* is an adverb or takes the place of an adverb (for example, negative, modal, tense), it cannot come before the verb in Chinese and occupy a place between the verb and its object.”⁵

The scholar also notes that the conjunction 是 *shì* can enter into a wide range of relationships with negations and modals. In the examples given below, the conjunction *shìshì* is considered as an emphasis: 小李是明天不去 [Xiǎo lǐ shì míngtiān bù qù] - *Xiaoli will not go tomorrow*; 小李不是明天去 [Xiǎo lǐ bùshì míngtiān qù] – *The day Xiaoli goes is not tomorrow*; 是 小李可能明天去 [Shì xiǎo lǐ kěnéng míngtiān qù] – *Xiaoli may go tomorrow*; 是 小李可能明天去 [Shì xiǎo lǐ kěnéng míngtiān qù] – *Maybe tomorrow is the day to go to Xiaoli*.

According to Huang, in these examples, the focus operator 是 *shì* conjunction, the negation operator 不 *bù* and the modal operator 可能 *kěnéng* freely interact with each other. This, in turn, shows that the conjunction 是 *shì* is another quantifier with a wide range of properties that interacts with negation and modal as well as other adverbs⁶.

Finally, Juan points out that although the element 是 *shì* has adverbial status, it is closely related to the linking verb 是 *shì* used in connected sentences, including pseudo-conjunctions. also with 是 *shì*. 她用了力了 [tā yòngle lìle] – Verb phrases like 用了 *yòngle* “to use force” in the example 她用力打小王 [tā yònglì dǎ xiǎo wáng] – *He hit Xiaowang with force* in the example can do its job.

Thus, in the above sentences, we can see that 是 *shì* systematically performs the function of linking verb. In this case, the subject of the noun phrase is referred to together with the main subject.

The most common conjunction in modern Chinese is the 是 *shì* conjunction. This conjunction is etymologically related to the demonstrative pronoun. Originally (in Middle Chinese), the negative form of the conjunction 是 *shì* was formed with the annotation 非 *fēi*, and the form 不 *bù* appeared much later. In Mandarin, the rate of use of the conjunction 是 *shì* is several times higher than the

⁴ O’sha asar

⁵ O’sha asar

⁶ O’sha asar

general rate of use of all other conjunctions: 这个人是他的父亲 [zhè gè rén shì tā de fùqīn] *This man is his father*; 那是谁? [nà shì shéi?] – *Who is he?*; 长江是中国的一大水 [Chángjiāng shì Zhōngguó de yī dàshuǐ] – *Yangtze is a major river in China.*⁷

Conjunction 是shì ("to be") and its synonym 在zài "to be in" (place) verb "to be located" as well as mental activity verbs 知道zhīdao "to know", 认识rènshi "to meet; know" is used only with the negation morpheme 不bù in any tense and aspectual context: 他不是中国人 [tā bù shì Zhōngguó rén] – *He is not Chinese*; 我不知道他要来 [wǒ bù zhīdào tā yào lái] – *I didn't know he was going to come*; 他小时候不认识她 [tā xiǎoshíhòu bù rènshi tā] – *He did not know her when he was young*; 昨天我不在家 [zuótiān wǒ bù zài jiā] – *I was not at home yesterday.*

The negation 没méi before 在zài "to be in" (place) is sometimes found in colloquial speech, although it is grammatically incorrect.⁸

Simple sentences in Chinese also consist of the subject of the sentence - the theme and its interpreter, that is, the remaining parts of the sentence, and these parts are connected by means of prepositional and exclamatory words. Han Weiren and Dingxui considered that the functional function of the predicate is a theme marker - a subject marker of the sentence in the description of Chinese sentences with the conjunction 是shì. According to them, in such sentences, the conjunction 是shì can give way to the preposition, as it participates in the same status as the preposition, that is, as a subject determiner. For example, 他是去年生的孩子 (he + conjunction+last year+birth+emphatic construction+child) 他呢, 去年生的孩子 (he+theme marker+last year+birth In both constructions (moq+emphasizing construction+child) the theme sign occurs, only in the first case there is an indicator indicating the border of theme and explanation, and in the second case there is 呢ne. From the point of view of the concept of predicativeness, in one of the recent studies of the Chinese language text, the ability to insert an adjunct between the subject and the comment while maintaining the nature of the sentence is considered as the main criterion.⁹

Like many other languages, Modern Chinese has conjunctions and conjunctive clauses. In the most general sense, a conjunction is necessary to record the confirmation of the relationship between the noun in the sentence and the infinitive, gerund, relative adjective and possessive adjective that can be used in its place. At the same time, in a number of cases, the Chinese language is considered to be a language with the ability to form participle sentences even without the participation of conjunctions, based on its feature of division of thematic sentences. A conjunction is not always needed when a noun and an adjective, a noun and an action noun are introduced into the possessive-participle relation in the structure of the sentence. According to the structure of the sentence, its use in sentences that do not need such a conjunction leads to a stronger emphasis on the part of the sentence.

According to generally accepted rules, by recording the relationship of mutual similarity between two realities or parts of reality, their belonging to a more general class or category is determined by means of connection.

In European languages, as a rule, a conjunction in a sentence is expressed using the forms of the verb "to be", therefore, a conjunction is often a combination of a conjunction and a past participle. a complex noun-participle structure is understood. In Uzbek linguistics, the conjunction is also involved in the noun-participle structure, the formal part of the participle, the means connecting the participle with the possessor, the participle forming, joined with non-verb words, modality, tense, mood, is defined as an auxiliary word expressing person-number meanings.

⁷ Крюков М. В., Хуан Шу-ин. Древнекитайский язык (тексты, грамматика, лексический комментарий) – М.: Наука, 1978. – С. 314-315.

⁸ 刁晏斌. 现代汉语虚义动词研究. 大连: 辽宁师范大学出版社, 2004. – 页 326.

⁹ Косик К.Э. Топиковые структуры в современных лингвистических парадигмах: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. Наук. – Москва, 2019. – 25 с.

Based on the positional morphology, almost all conjunctions in Chinese can be considered to be inflected according to the verb. Most of them are linking units made of yukalam or an auxiliary verb, and the element shìshì is distinguished from others by taking the role of the main link.

The main and “most normative” conjunction for modern Chinese is the unsure, although in many cases it exhibits all the necessary "verb-connector" features, and is etymologically not a verb. It acquired its current functional role in the history of the Chinese language in the 4th century IV.

There are a number of opinions about the place and content of the conjunction 是shì, but not all of them agree..

The conjunction 是shì, unlike verbs, does not take modifiers, and modal verbs are not placed before the conjunction 是shì.

曾经 céngjīng, 将来 jiānglái can be added before the conjunction 是shì to express the meaning of time/aspect: 我曾经是工地上的工人 [wǒ céngjīng shì gōngdì shàng de gōngrén] – *I used to be a construction worker*; 我们的小龙将来是个外交家 [wǒmen de Xiǎolóng jiāng lái shì gè wàijiāo jiā] – *Our Xiao Long will be a diplomat in the future.*

The conjunction 是shì can also come before adverbs with the meaning of changing, clarifying, limiting the predication: 我也是工人 [wǒ yěshì gōngrén] – *I am also a worker.*

We can add 就jiù (便biàn) “exactly”, 才cái “just now”, 只zhǐ “only” to the sentence of words defined above: 他就是小明 [tā jiùshì xiǎomíng] – *He is Xiao Ming*; 一病就是半个月 [yī bìng jiùshì bàn gè yuè] – *The half moon got sick.*

Most importantly, the conjunction 是shì cannot be used repeatedly in the same sentence.

The negative form of the conjunction 是shì is formed in the form 不是 bùshì only by combining with 不 bù. However, méishì is not possible in the form of 没是 méi shì, because the conjunction 是shì is not an independent verb and it cannot take the perfect form: 他不是昨天来的 [tā bùshì zuótiān lái de] – *He did not come yesterday*; 学校对面不是公园 [xué jiào duìmiàn bùshì gōngyuán] – *Not the park in front of the school.*

The written equivalents of 不是 bùshì are 非fēi and 否fǒu (是否=是不是): 这件事作你所能解决 [zhè jiàn shì zuò nǐ suǒ néng jiějué] – *This work is beyond my authority*; 两人很亲切 · 看来非亲即友 [liǎng rén hěn qīnqiè, kàn lái fēi qīn jí yǒu] – *These two are very close, not direct relatives, but friends*; 是否可以? [shìfǒu kěyǐ?] – *Is it possible or not?*

Conjunctive derivation is the process of forming a grammatical structure through a connective, which involves a topic-based reanalysis structure and is a case of re-formation and re-categorization, i.e., the connection shìshì occurs as a result of expressing the subject anaphora with the demonstrative pronoun 是shì.

FOYDANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI:

1. Randolph Quirk, Sidney Greenbaum, Geoffrey Leech and Jan Svartvik. A Comprehensive Grammar of English language. – London and New York: Longman. 1985. – 1779 p.; Stephen Levinson. Pragmatics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983. – P. 301-314.
2. Amanda Patten. Cleft Sentences, construction grammar and grammaticalization. – Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh, 2010. – P. 45-50.
3. Narahaga Tomiko. The Japanese copula: Forms and Functions. – New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2002. – P. 165-178.

4. Shou-Hsin Teng. Remarks on cleft sentences in Chinese//Journal of Chinese linguistics: 7.1. 1979. – P.101-114.; Yao Zhu. The Focus-marking function of shi in mandarin Chinese. Phd dissertation. – Mankato: University of Minnesota. 1997. – 198 p.; James Huang. Logical Relations in Chinese and the Theory of Grammar. – New York: Garland publishing, 1998. – P. 128-143.
5. Крюков М. В., Хуан Шу-ин. Древнекитайский язык (тексты, грамматика, лексический комментарий) – М.: Наука, 1978. – С. 314-315.
6. 刁晏斌. 现代汉语虚义动词研究. 大连: 辽宁师范大学出版社, 2004. – 页 326.
7. Косик К.Э. Топиковые структуры в современных лингвистических парадигмах: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. Наук. – Москва, 2019. – 25 с.
8. Sodiqov B. Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tilida bog‘lama. – Т.: Fan, 1984. – В. 7.
9. Курдюмов В.А. Курс китайского языка Теоретическая грамматика. – М.: Ситадель-тресей, 2005. – С. 575.